

UTILIZATION OF ROPPASPARA (*Mikania cordata*) LEAF EXTRACT AS ALTERNATIVE MEDICINE IN TREATING WOUNDS ON MICE

Wardatul Aini (1910423019) – Laboratorium Teaching 4, Jurusan Biologi, FMIPA
Universitas Andalas

Indonesia's vast nature provides a lot of natural potential that has not been utilized optimally. Many plants in Indonesia contain medicinal and healing substances, one of which is Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) leaf. Extracts from the leaves of Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) will be used as an alternative medicine in treating external wounds to mice. This paper has the theme of the field of animal physiology and the field of plant physiology. I support this for several reasons. First, the leaves of Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) has many benefits and used as medicine in some areas. Second, the leaves of Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) are abundant in nature, but have not been utilized properly. Third, the injuries are things that often happen.

The leaves of Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) has many benefits and used as medicine in some areas. Dusun Montong, District Na. IX-X, North Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra is one of the regions in Indonesia with the majority of the population working as rubber tappers. While working, sometimes injuries occur due to being slashed by a cutting knife. When this happens, people immediately look for plants that are able to reduce pain in wounds, namely roppaspara leaves (*Mikania cordata*) by local residents because these plants can heal wounds quickly. *Mikania cordata* leaves are also able to treat stomach pain and itching used by Malaysians. In Africa the leaves can be used as a soup. In addition, this weed is used to cover rubber plantations in Malaysia. This plant is also deliberately planted on slopes to prevent soil erosion. It was also reported from Mizoram, India that *Mikania cordata* can be used as green manure to increase good rice yields. However, this plant cannot be used as a compost mixture because of its high water content (Sankaran, 2010). This plant has quite a lot of good benefits in the world of medicine. This plant can provide efficacy as an antibacterial.

The leaves of Roppaspara (*Mikania Cordata*) are abundant in nature, but have not been utilized properly. The Roppaspara leaf grows as a weed, so not many people know the use of this plant. Roppaspara (*Mikania cordata*) is a creeping shrub that can be found in various areas in the Province Bali. This plant is very popular with livestock cattle, easy to breed and heavy production high fresh. In various fields or land this plant plantation grows

fresh and lush and can also act as cover plants soil to prevent increased transport sediment during heavy rains. Mikania stems (*Mikania cordata*) grow light green, branched and overgrown with fine hairs. The length of the stem can reach 3-6m. In each internode there are two opposite leaves, a new shoot and a flower. The leaves are triangular in shape resembling a heart, with a leaf length of 4-13cm, and a leaf width of 2-9cm. The leaf surface resembles a bowl with serrated leaf edges, and the leaves are incomplete. Flowers grow white, small with a length of 4.5-6 mm, and grow from the leaf axils or at the tip of the shoot. Seeds produced in large quantities, blackish brown with a length of 2 mm. The fruit is ovoid inverted, green, measuring 1-3 mm, the fruit is a true fruit, and has a thin seed coat. Besides *Mikania cordata*, there is also *Mikania 77 micracanta* which is known as an introduction weed. The weed comes from South America which first entered into Indonesia (Bogor Botanical Garden) from Paraguay in 1949. By 1956 the plant had spread area as a ground cover crop on plantations rubber (Whitten et al., 2000).

The next is the injuries are things that often happen, so that by finding alternatives in wound healing, this can be used as a way of treating wounds. Injuries can occur in daily activities which can be caused by: scratched, sliced, cut, etc. Scratches occur due to sharp objects such as glass or wire. Treating wounds aims to prevent damage to the skin, membranes mucosa or other tissues caused by trauma, fracture, injury surgery that can damage the skin surface De Jong (2010). Under care wounds can use non-pharmacological therapy by utilizing plants efficacious medicine because it is more effective, easy to obtain, affordable prices.

Based on the description that has been presented above, I would like to better understand the effectiveness of *Ropaspara* leaves as an alternative in treating wounds in mice. It is hoped that this paper can be useful for many people.

REFERENCE

Rahma, Umi. 2011. Mikania Cordata. <http://umi89rahmah.blogspot.co.id/2011/05/2.html>, diakses 4 Juni 2021.

Sjamsuhidajat,R., Wim de Jong. (2010). Buku Ajar Ilmu Bedah, Edisi 3.Jakarta: EGC.

Whitten, T., R.E. Soeriaatmadja, S.A. Afiff. 2000. The Ecology of Java and Bali. Vol. II. Periplus Editions (HK) Ltd.